

science and policy
for a healthy future

Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation

Deliverable Report

AD14.6

WP14 - Effect Biomarkers

Deadline: January 2020

Upload by Coordinator: 28 April 2020

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marika Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	20/04/2020
Grant Signatory	Argelia Castaño	ISCIII	26/01/2020

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Robert Barouki	INSERM	13/02/2020
Work Package Leader	Mariana F. Fernández	UGR	26/01/2020
Task leader	Mariana F. Fernández	UGR	26/01/2020

Responsible author	Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández
Short name of institution	UGR
Co-authors	Shereen Cynthia (INSERM), Louis Legoff (INSERM), Fatima Smagulova (INSERM), Arthur David (INSERM), Eva Cecilie Bonfeld-Jorgensen (AU), Maria Wilsoe (AU), Anne Kjerstine Rosenmai (DTU), Anne Marie Vinggaard (DTU)

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 2

Table of contents

Table of contents	2
1 Authors and acknowledgements.....	3
2 Abstract/Summary	4
3 Introduction	5
4 Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) as a candidate novel biomarker for neurodevelopment (UGR).....	6
4.1.1 Study population, materials and methods	7
4.1.2 Results	7
4.1.3 References	11
5 Epigenetic measurements in the blood of INMA-GRANADA Boys (INSERM)	14
5.1 PART I.....	14
5.1.1 Results	14
5.1.2 References	16
5.2 PART II.....	16
5.2.1 Characterisation of the Effect Biomarker: Histone Modifications	16
5.2.2 Results	16
5.2.3 References	18
5.3 PART III.....	19
5.3.1 Characterisation of the Effect Biomarker: Telomere Length	19
5.3.2 Methodology and Procedure	19
5.3.3 Results	19
5.3.4 References	20
5.4 Conclusions from the epigenetic measurements in the blood of INMA-GRANADA Boys	20
6 Antagonistic AR activity in placenta samples (UGR-DTU)	21
6.1.1 Strategy, materials and methods.....	21
6.1.2 Results	24
6.1.3 References	27
7 Xenoestrogenic transactivity of placenta extracts containing PFAS mixtures (AU).....	28
7.1.1 Description of the Bioassay/Effect Biomarker	28
7.1.2 Methodology and Procedure	28
7.1.3 Results	29
7.1.4 Strengths and limitations	31
7.1.5 Conclusions.....	31
7.1.6 References	31
8 Conclusions and Future Steps.....	33

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 3

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo (UGR)

Vicente Mustieles (UGR)

Nicolás Olea (UGR)

Mariana F. Fernández (UGR)

Contributors

Shereen Cynthia D’Cruz (INSERM)

Louis Legoff (INSERM)

Fatima Smagulova (INSERM)

Arthur David (INSERM)

Eva Cecilie Bonfeld-Jorgensen (AU)

Maria Wilsoe (AU)

Anne Kjerstine Rosenmai (DTU)

Anne Marie Vinggaard (DTU)

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 4

2 Abstract/Summary

Background: WP14 is investigating the use and implementation of both classical and novel effect biomarkers that can address previous data gaps identified, providing an added value to HBM studies.

Objective: The current deliverable aims to present the state of development of Task 14.3: “Identification of needs for the implementation of only new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation”, consisting on the experimental work related to some of the new effect biomarkers undertaken in WP14 during 2019.

Methods: Novel biomarkers (as brain-derived neurotrophic factor, BDNF) were fine-tuned in order to investigate the appropriated quality and assessment conditions before its implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies. Regarding biomarkers of combined activity to chemical mixtures, an effect-directed analysis identified the subfractions of the previously whole extracted alpha-fraction from placentas (D14.4 and AD14.4) with the highest antiandrogenic activity. Additionally, a method to isolate and assess xenoestrogenic combined activity of mixtures of PFAS compounds from the same placentas samples was developed.

Results: The preliminary data with the INMA-Granada blood and serum samples shows the technical feasibility to implement novel biomarkers of brain function, as BDNF, at different levels of biological organisation, although at this stage, no conclusions for its applicability can be taken. Moreover, the use of cell-based bioassays may help to better understand how chemical mixtures contained in human samples may exert combined biological activities, allowing also identifying both known and new chemicals of concern in human tissues.

Conclusions: The pilot study with INMA-Granada samples has demonstrated the technical feasibility to implement novel biomarkers of brain function such as BDNF, at different levels of biological organisation, in HBM4EU aligned studies. Moreover, the use of cell-based bioassays may help to better understand how specific chemical mixtures contained in human samples may exert combined hormonal activities. Finally, the development of chemical’s mixture isolation, such as PFAS, opens the possibility of assessing specific chemical families isolated from human samples, with potential implications for risk assessment and policy making.

Future Steps: i) To implement novel biomarkers of brain function in the HBM4EU aligned studies based on the results obtained with the INMA-Granada pilot study; ii) To analyse and integrate all exposure, effect and outcome data available for neurodevelopment in the INMA-Granada study; iii) To identify the chemical profile of the placental subfractions showing the highest antiandrogenic activities, through the use of non-targeted chemical methods under the interaction with WP16 partners; iv) Further test other biological activities of the isolated mixture of PFAS from placenta samples, and explore the isolation of other chemical families in other more convenient biological samples for HBM studies such as blood and urine samples.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 5

3 Introduction

Among the main aims of WP14 (Effect biomarkers) are the identification of gaps in knowledge related to effect biomarkers, and the implementation and/or research on novel or understudied effect biomarkers that can address those data gaps providing an added value to HBM studies. Based on the previous comprehensive literature searches (D14.2), two of the big identified gaps in knowledge were:

1. Limited effect biomarkers for brain function (with BDNF as a promising candidate).
2. Limited data on biomarkers of combined activity to assess the biological effect of complex chemical mixtures in human biological samples.

The current deliverable presents the state of development of Task 14.3, titled: ““Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation”, consisting on the experimental work undertaken in WP14 during 2019 to cover the previously identified gaps in knowledge (D14.2).

First, we present the results of the pilot study for the possible implementation of novel biomarkers for neurodevelopment: levels of BDNF at different levels of biological organisation (DNA, RNA, circulating proteins, etc.) in several biological samples from adolescent boys belonging to the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort. UGR (WP14 partner) has assessed serum total BDNF levels, while INSERM has assessed DNA methylation of BDNF in blood, as well as histone modifications related to BDNF gene expression. Additionally, other relevant and novel molecular targets identified in D14.2, such as nuclear receptors and telomere length, were implemented in the same adolescent blood samples by INSERM partners.

Second, we extended previous data regarding biomarkers of combined biological activity for chemical mixtures. Although there is growing concern that human exposure to chemical mixtures could increase the risk of adverse health effects, researchers primarily study chemicals as if exposure occurs individually. This one compound-at-a-time approach has left us with insufficient knowledge regarding potential perjudicial effects exerted by mixtures of environmental chemicals. As part of the HBM4EU WP14-16 collaboration, we first reviewed the state-of-the-art knowledge and experience on associating bioassay activities measured in human tissues with adverse human health outcome (i.e. bioassays used as biomarkers of effect) (article under preparation).

Thus, this work continues the one showed in D14.4, the “placenta proof of concept”, with two additional aims: 1) To conduct an effect-directed analysis to identify placenta subfractions with the highest antiandrogenic activity (UGR + DTU partners); and ii) To develop a new method to isolate mixtures of PFAS compounds from placental samples, and assess their combined xenoestrogenic activity.

This deliverable updates the active lines of research inside WP14, showing how these are interdependently arranged to accomplish WP14 aims inside the HBM4EU initiative.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 6

4 Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) as a candidate novel biomarker for neurodevelopment (UGR)

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), is a growth factor from the family of neurotrophins. This neurotrophic factor can play an important role in neurogenesis, neurite growth, synaptic transmission, synaptic plasticity, brain development and learning and memory processes among others (Bathina and Das, 2015; Lu et al., 2014). After its synthesis by the endoplasmic reticulum and posterior intracellular cleavage, BDNF can be secreted in two isoforms: mature BDNF and pro-BDNF, which biological functions can be antagonistic depending on the stage of development of the central nervous system (Foltran and Diaz, 2016; Mizui et al., 2016). Both BDNF isoforms follow a dynamic balance during the entire life and development of the organism (Yang et al., 2014).

Figure 1: Secretion and intra-extracellular maturation procedures of BDNF

Additionally, BDNF has also been implicated in neuropsychiatric disorders related with an altered behaviour (Autry and Monteggia, 2012). Similarly, changes in the expression of BDNF have been reported in several neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer disease, Parkinson disease and Huntington disease (Zuccato and Cattaneo, 2009).

Furthermore, BDNF has been associated with the exposure to some chemical pollutants such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) or perfluorooctanoic acids (PFOS) (Li et al., 2015; Perera et al., 2015; Sram et al., 2017).

BDNF has been easily measured in serum and urine samples through immunosorbent assays. Based on Polacchino et al. data, we selected the most appropriated immunosorbent assay kit, according to recovery, range values and intra- and inter-assay variations data (Polacchini et al., 2015). Additionally, with the aim to diminish the amount required of human samples, we have made some trials with different sample volumes. As a result, UGR has fine-tuned the methodology based on immunosorbent assays to quantify this neurotrophic factor in serum and urine samples in the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 7

4.1.1 Study population, materials and methods

4.1.1.1 Study Population

The Spanish INMA-Granada birth cohort includes 668 mother-son pairs recruited at delivery (2000–2002) at the San Cecilio University Hospital in the province of Granada, Spain (Fernandez et al., 2007). To date, the INMA-Granada birth cohort has included several follow-ups since recruitment. All families from the cohort were re-contacted and asked to participate in follow-up visits at the ages of 4–5 years ($n = 220$) (Freire et al., 2010) and 9–11 years ($n = 300$) (Mustieles et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Carrillo et al., 2019). During the last follow up visit (2017-2019) at the age 15–17 years, 155 males adolescents agreed to participate and underwent to physical and psychological examination at the San Cecilio University Hospital. Both children and parents gave their written informed consent.

4.1.1.2 Materials and Methods

Whole venous blood was collected from participants ($n=134$) at 5-7 PM and was then processed, and stored at -80°C . We have measured total serum BDNF concentration with an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using a Quantikine® ELISA kit (R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA). Serum samples were aliquoted in $20\ \mu\text{L}$ and diluted 1:100 times before proceeding with the ELISA Kit. Afterwards, total BDNF were measured according to the manufacturer's instructions.

4.1.2 Results

Serum BDNF levels ranged from 14.25 ng/mL to 65.75 ng/ml, and mean and geometric mean were 34.8 and 33.7 ng/mL, respectively. Distribution of total serum BDNF concentrations were as follows: $P25^{\text{th}} = 29.1\ \text{ng/mL}$, $P50^{\text{th}} = 34.6\ \text{ng/mL}$ and $P75^{\text{th}} = 39.7\ \text{ng/mL}$ (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of serum BDNF concentration (ng/mL) in adolescents from the INMA-Granada cohort, ($n=134$). On the left, it is shown the dispersion of the concentrations of serum BDNF. On the right, the range of BDNF concentrations in serum among the participants is shown in a histogram.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 8

4.1.2.1 Comparison with serum BDNF levels from previous epidemiologic studies

In order to assess the comparability of the obtained serum BDNF concentrations, UGR conducted a brief search of the scientific data, based on PubMed. The objective of this brief search was to look for levels of serum BDNF previously published and compare them with the levels obtained from the INMA-Granada cohort.

Briefly, inclusion criteria were: i) scientific articles published in the last 10 years; ii) epidemiological studies; iii) BDNF should have been measured in serum samples with immunosorbent assays and iv) only measures of BDNF concentrations from healthy people will be included. If the study was a randomised control trial, only data from controls was included. Search terms included (brain-derived neurotrophic factor OR BDNF) AND (serum AND adolescents).

Table 1: Serum BDNF levels found in the scientific literature from epidemiological studies

Study			BDNF Concentration	Isoform	Sample	Methodology
Author	Study Design	Population	Media			
Kim et al., 2016	Case-control study	Controls n=9 adolescents 16.3 years old	20.9 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	R&D system (Minneapolis, MN, USA) kit using a Sino Biological kit (Sino Biological Inc., Beijing, China)
Naegelin et al., 2018	Methodological study	259 healthy participants; 44.31 years old	Female 32.9 ng/mL Males 32.3 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Combination of BDNF monoclonal antibodies designated mAb BDNF-#1 and mAb BDNF-#9 (Kolbeck et al., 1999).
Pedersen et al., 2017	Cross-sectional study	447 healthy adolescents 11-17 years old	Female 26.9 ng/mL Male 27 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Quantikine, R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA
Piccini et al., 2008	Descriptive Study	28 adults (Men=28-32 years old; Women=25-32 years old)	Plasma: Male 7.82 ng/ml Female 5.48 ng/ml Serum: Male 38.1 ng/ml Female 37 ng/ml	Total BDNF	Plasma and serum	Promega, Wallisellen, Switzerland
Huang et al., 2017	Cross-sectional study	Boys and girls (n=415), 14 years old	Boys= 27.3ng/mL Girls= 26.8 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Quantikine® ELISA, R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA
Oddone et al., 2016	Case-control study	Controls= 15 (62.2 years)	Values 313.6 pg/ml	Total BDNF	Serum	ELISA (code DY248; sensitivity 20pg/ml; R&D System)

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 9

Study			BDNF Concentration	Isoform	Sample	Methodology
Author	Study Design	Population	Media			
Cho et al., 2017	Case-control prepuberal 11-12 yrs old	Cases=30 ; Controls= 15 (both at 9-12 years)	Case 24.45 ng/ml Control 24.00 ng/ml	Total BDNF	Serum	Quantikine Kit (Catalog No. DBD00; R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA)
Zhao et al., 2017	Case-control study	44 healthy controls, 29.2 years old	m-BDNF= 353.8 pg/mL; p-BDNF= 92.13 pg/mL; Ratio m/po= 4.6	m-BDNF; p-BDNF; Ratio m/p	Plasma	ELISA kits(Shanghai Bogoo Biotechnology Co., Ltd. Shanghai, China) (Code number: HEB005 and HEP142 for mBDNF anf proBDNF respectively)
Fonseca-Portilla et al., 2019	Case-control Study	active women= 195; 40 yrs old; non active women= 154 40 yrs old	active: 33 ng/mL; non active 34 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Applied Biosystems, CA
Ormstad et al., 2018	Case-control study	n= 30 children; 10.9 years	BDNF 21.2 ng/mL; pro-BDNF= 4.9 ng/mL	BDNF and PRO-BDNF	Serum	Plasma levels of BDNF and PRO-BDNF were assessed using Derived Neurotrophic Factor ELISA kit and Human Pro Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor ELISA kit obtained Nordic BioSite, Sweden.
Mora et al., 2019	Case-control study	n= 49 healthy controls; 48.3 years old	40.0 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	sandwich-ELISA, using a commercial kit according to the manufacturer's instructions (Chemicon, Temecula, CA, USA),
Yurteri et al., 2019	Case-control study	24 boys with 10.5 years old	BDNF 14.87 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay: Fine Biological Technology Co. Ltd, cat. No: EH-0043
Aksu et al., 2018	Case-control study	30 adolescent 14.7 years old	1.04 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	Human BDNF ELISA Kit (Boster Immunoleader, USA),
Alomari et al., 2018	Cross-sectional study	288 healthy adolescents 14 years old	Boys 11 µg/dL Girls 15 µg/dL	BDNF	Serum	Human BDNF Duoset Kit R&D system, USA

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 10

Study			BDNF Concentration	Isoform	Sample	Methodology
Author	Study Design	Population	Media			
Jein et al., 2017	Randomized control trial	49 healthy male 15 years old	27.04 ng/mL	BDNF	Serum	ELISA (sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbant assay) Kit (Promega, USA)

Summary

BDNF levels measured in serum samples from INMA-Granada cohort were= 33.7 ng/mL (GM).

BDNF serum levels were within the range of some previous published studies.

In plasma samples, BDNF concentration is lower than in serum.

Total BDNF is the most measured isoform in epidemiological studies

The ratio of pre/pro BDNF should be measured as a more specific biomarker to address neurodevelopment

BDNF could be an ideal candidate as a novel biomarker of effect for neurodevelopment within the HBM4EU context.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 11

4.1.3 References

- Aksu, S., Unlu, G., Kardesler, A.C., Cakaloz, B., Aybek, H., 2018. Altered levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor, proBDNF and tissue plasminogen activator in children with posttraumatic stress disorder. *Psychiatry Res.* 268, 478–483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2018.07.013>
- Alomari, M.A., Al-sheyab, N.A., Khabour, O.F., Alzoubi, K.H., 2018. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in adolescents smoking waterpipe: The Irbid TRY. *Int. J. Dev. Neurosci.* 67, 14–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdevneu.2018.03.007>
- Autry, A.E., Monteggia, L.M., 2012. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor and neuropsychiatric disorders. *Pharmacol. Rev.* 64, 238–58. <https://doi.org/10.1124/pr.111.005108>
- Bathina, S., Das, U.N., 2015. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor and its clinical implications. *Arch. Med. Sci.* 6, 1164–1178. <https://doi.org/10.5114/aoms.2015.56342>
- Cho, S.Y., So, W.Y., Roh, H.T., 2017. The effects of taekwondo training on peripheral Neuroplasticity-Related growth factors, cerebral blood flow velocity, and cognitive functions in healthy children: A randomized controlled trial. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14050454>
- Fernandez, M.F., Molina-Molina, J.M., Lopez-Espinosa, M.-J., Freire, C., Campoy, C., Ibarluzea, J., Torne, P., Pedraza, V., Olea, N., 2007. Biomonitoring of environmental estrogens in human tissues. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 210, 429–432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2007.01.014>
- Foltran, R.B., Diaz, S.L., 2016. BDNF isoforms: a round trip ticket between neurogenesis and serotonin? *J. Neurochem.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnc.13658>
- Fonseca-Portilla, R., Krell-Roesch, J., Shaibi, G.Q., Caselli, R.J., Mandarino, L.J., Zhang, N., Hentz, J.G., Coletta, D.K., De Filippis, E.A., Dawit, S., Geda, Y.E., 2019. Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor and its associations with metabolism and physical activity in a Latino sample. *Metab. Syndr. Relat. Disord.* 17, 75–80. <https://doi.org/10.1089/met.2018.0028>
- Freire, C., Ramos, R., Amaya, E., Fernández, M.F., Santiago-Fernández, P., Lopez-Espinosa, M.J., Arrebola, J.P., Olea, N., 2010. Newborn TSH concentration and its association with cognitive development in healthy boys. *Eur. J. Endocrinol.* 163, 901–909. <https://doi.org/10.1530/EJE-10-0495>
- Huang, T., Gejl, A.K., Tarp, J., Andersen, L.B., Peijs, L., Bugge, A., 2017. Cross-sectional associations of objectively measured physical activity with brain-derived neurotrophic factor in adolescents. *Physiol. Behav.* 171, 87–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2016.12.026>
- Jeon, Y.K., Ha, C.H., 2017. The effect of exercise intensity on brain derived neurotrophic factor and memory in adolescents. *Environ. Health Prev. Med.* 22, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-017-0643-6>
- Kim, Y. Il, 2016. The impact of exercise training on basal bdnf in athletic adolescents. *J. Phys. Ther. Sci.* 28, 3066–3069. <https://doi.org/10.1589/jpts.28.3066>
- Li, W., He, Q.Z., Wu, C.Q., Pan, X.Y., Wang, J., Tan, Y., Shan, X.Y., Zeng, H.C., 2015. PFOS Disturbs BDNF-ERK-CREB Signalling in association with increased microRNA-22 in SH-SY5Y Cells. *Biomed Res. Int.* 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/302653>
- Lu, B., Nagappan, G., Lu, Y., 2014. BDNF and Synaptic Plasticity, Cognitive Function, and Dysfunction, in: *Handbook of Experimental Pharmacology*. pp. 223–250. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-45106-5_9
- Mizui, T., Ishikawa, Y., Kumanogoh, H., Kojima, M., 2016. Neurobiological actions by three distinct subtypes of brain-derived neurotrophic factor: Multi-ligand model of growth factor signaling. *Pharmacol. Res.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2015.12.019>

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 12

- Mora, E., Portella, M.J., Piñol-Ripoll, G., López, R., Cuadras, D., Forcada, I., Teres, M., Vieta, E., Mur, M., 2019. High BDNF serum levels are associated to good cognitive functioning in bipolar disorder. *Eur. Psychiatry* 60, 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2019.02.006>
- Mustieles, V., Casas, M., Ferrando-Marco, P., Ocón-Hernández, O., Reina-Pérez, I., Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., Vela-Soria, F., Pérez-Lobato, R., Navarrete-Muñoz, E.M., Freire, C., Olea, N., Fernández, M.F., 2019. Bisphenol A and adiposity measures in peripubertal boys from the INMA-Granada cohort. *Environ. Res.* 443–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.03.045>
- Naegelin, Y., Dingsdale, H., Säuberli, K., Schädelin, S., Kappos, L., Barde, Y.A., 2018. Measuring and validating the levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor in human serum. *eNeuro* 5, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0419-17.2018>
- Oddone, F., Roberti, G., Micera, A., Busanello, A., Bonini, S., Quaranta, L., Agnifili, L., Manni, G., 2017. Exploring serum levels of Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor and nerve growth factor across glaucoma stages. *PLoS One* 12, e0168565. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0168565>
- Ormstad, H., Bryn, V., Verkerk, R., Skjeldal, O.H., Halvorsen, B., Saugstad, O.D., Isaksen, J., Maes, M., 2018. Serum tryptophan, tryptophan catabolites and brain-derived neurotrophic factor in subgroups of youngsters with autism spectrum disorders. *CNS Neurol. Disord. - Drug Targets* 17, 626–639. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1871527317666180720163221>
- Pedersen, N.H., Tarp, J., Andersen, L.B., Gejl, A.K., Huang, T., Peijs, L., Bugge, A., 2017. The association between serum brain-derived neurotrophic factor and a cluster of cardiovascular risk factors in adolescents: The CHAMPS-study DK. *PLoS One* 12, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186384>
- Perera, F., Phillips, D.H., Wang, Y., Roen, E., Herbstman, J., Rauh, V., Wang, S., Tang, D., 2015. Prenatal exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons/aromatics, BDNF and child development. *Environ. Res.* 142, 602–608. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.08.011>
- Piccinni, A., Marazziti, D., Del Debbio, A., Bianchi, C., Roncaglia, I., Mannari, C., Origlia, N., Catena Dell’Osso, M., Massimetti, G., Domenici, L., Dell’Osso, L., 2008. Diurnal variation of plasma brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) in humans: An analysis of sex differences. *Chronobiol. Int.* 25, 819–826. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07420520802387773>
- Polacchini, A., Metelli, G., Francavilla, R., Baj, G., Florean, M., Mascaretti, L.G., Tongiorgi, E., 2015. A method for reproducible measurements of serum BDNF: comparison of the performance of six commercial assays. *Sci. Rep.* 5:17989. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep17989>
- Rodríguez-Carrillo, A., Mustieles, V., Pérez-Lobato, R., Molina-Molina, J.M., Reina-Pérez, I., Vela-Soria, F., Rubio, S., Olea, N., Fernández, M.F., 2019. Bisphenol A and cognitive function in school-age boys: Is BPA predominantly related to behavior? *Neurotoxicology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2019.06.006>
- Sram, R.J., Veleminsky, M. Jr., Veleminsky, M. Sr., Stejskalová, J. 2017. The impact of air pollution to central nervous system in children and adults. *Neuro Endocrinol Lett.* 238(6):389–396.
- Yang, J., Harte-Hargrove, L.C., Siao, C.J., Marinic, T., Clarke, R., Ma, Q., Jing, D., LaFrancois, J.J., Bath, K.G., Mark, W., Ballon, D., Lee, F.S., Scharfman, H.E., Hempstead, B.L., 2014. ProBDNF negatively regulates neuronal remodeling, synaptic transmission, and synaptic plasticity in hippocampus. *Cell Rep.* 7, 796–806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2014.03.040>
- Yurteri, N., Şahin, İ.E., Tufan, A.E., 2019. Altered serum levels of vascular endothelial growth factor and glial-derived neurotrophic factor but not fibroblast growth factor-2 in treatment-naive children with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Nord. J. Psychiatry* 73, 302–307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08039488.2019.1625437>

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 13

Zuccato, C., Cattaneo, E., 2009. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in neurodegenerative diseases. *Nat. Rev. Neurol.* 5, 311–22. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrneurol.2009.54>

Zhao, G., Zhang, C., Chen, J., Su, Y., Zhou, R., Wang, F., Xia, W., Huang, J., Wang, Z., Hu, Y., Cao, L., Guo, X., Yuan, C., Wang, Y., Yi, Z., Lu, W., Wu, Y., Wu, Z., Hong, W., Peng, D., Fang, Y., 2017. Ratio of mBDNF to proBDNF for differential diagnosis of major depressive disorder and bipolar depression. *Mol. Neurobiol.* 54, 5573–5582. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-016-0098-6>

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 14

5 Epigenetic measurements in the blood of INMA-GRANADA Boys (INSERM)

5.1 PART I

As a preliminary approach, INSERM has analysed BDNF IV promoter DNA methylation in 124 DNA from the blood of the same boys from the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort by using pyrosequencing (no more blood sample were available for 10 boys out of 134 with BDNF data). Briefly, DNA was bisulfite converted, amplified using biotinylated BDNF primers, and sequenced using pyrosequencing technique to identify the percentage of methylation at six CpGs in Exon IV of BDNF.

Figure 3: Percentage of methylation in whole blood

5.1.1 Results

Before sequencing, the amplified and purified BDNF products for 124 samples were loaded on a 2% agarose gel and a single product was observed which indicates the BDNF primer specificity and absence of primer-dimers (one example is provided in Fig. 3).

The results of pyrosequencing were analysed and presented as percentage of methylation compared to unmethylated residue. Figure 4 shows the scatter plot indicating the percentage of DNA methylation for the six CpGs in BDNF Exon IV for INMA samples.

Figure 4: Percentage of DNA methylation for the six CpGs in BDNF Exon IV for several INMA samples

The distribution of the percentage of DNA methylation in the study population (n=119) (insufficient sample availability) was different for the 6 CpGs studied, with a minimum fold change observed for CpG6 and a maximum fold change observed for CpG 4 (CpG6= 1,374; CpG4= 1,560; fold change compared to average methylation for all 6 CpGs). Hypermethylation of BDNF was observed in small numbers of individual for each CpG island (Table 2). These results showed that majority of samples in each CpG position have similar methylation pattern, however, for each CpG, it was found some hypermethylated samples (Table 2), suggesting that DNA methylation was increased at least in some samples due to some factors that will be further investigated. For example, the increase in BDNF methylation was found in a previous study in children whose mothers were depressed during pregnancy (Braithwaite et al., 2015).

Table 2: Percentage of DNA methylation for six studied CpGs in the study population (n=119)

	CpG1	CpG2	CpG3	CpG4	CpG5	CpG6
Average	4.51	3.28	3.38	6.11	3.36	2.85
SD	0.83	0.44	0.58	1.22	0.75	1.06
SEM	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.11	0.07	0.09
1st quartile	3.93	2.97	2.97	5.35	2.75	2.11
3rd quartile	4.94	3.52	3.78	6.35	3.72	3.25
Interquartile range	1.00	0.56	0.81	1.00	0.97	1.14
# hypermethylated samples	5	2	1	10	2	5

It will explore if there is any correlation between % of DNA methylation of the studied CpG islands and BDNF protein levels measured by ELISA, in both serum and urine samples. DNA methylation at BDNF Exon IV showed alterations in CpGs in some of the tested samples. The data will be re-analysed by, for example, grouping the samples based on low and high-exposure to prioritised chemical compounds, as soon as exposure data is available.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 16

At this stage, no conclusions for a possible applicability of the BDNF IV promoter DNA methylation marker for HBM4EU settings can be taken.

5.1.2 References

Braithwaite EC, Kundakovic M, Ramchandani PG, Murphy SE, Champagne FA. 2015. Maternal prenatal depressive symptoms predict infant NR3C1 1F and BDNF IV DNA methylation. *Epigenetics* 10(5):408-417.

5.2 PART II

5.2.1 Characterisation of the Effect Biomarker: Histone Modifications

In the attempt to characterise BDNF as a candidate effect biomarker, INSERM analysed histone H3K4me3 occupancy at the promoters of genes from 200 µl blood from the INMA-Granada cohort because this mark has been associated with active gene transcription. Briefly, using chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP), the H3K4me3 associated DNA was isolated from blood, quantity was measured and equal amount of starting or immunoprecipitated DNA was taken for qPCR. For the analysis, we chose the primers in promoters of genes, which are associated with nuclear receptors, DNA damage and detoxification activities related functions.

The data was analysed with the help of Bio-Rad CFX Manager software. A good melt curve with a single amplicon could be observed for all the PCR products indicating the specificity of the primers and the absence of primer-dimers. We used as control, the region of *GAPDH* gene that is located far from the transcription start site. In general, the amplified PCR in this region represent the background and could be used for normalisation.

5.2.2 Results

The normalised target copy number data with *GAPDH* as the reference gene was obtained for all the samples. The basic measurement of ChIP experiment functioning is “immunoprecipitation efficiency” or “ChIP: input ratio” for a given genomic region, which is defined as the amount of PCR product in the ChIP sample divided by the amount of PCR product in the input sample. There was high enrichment for most of the analysed genes, indicating the efficiency of ChIP experiment.

Classification of samples into three groups based on analyses of H3K4me3 mark at *H2AFX* promoter (a marker of DNA damage): the *H2AFX* gene was analysed and plotted the normalised values in a cluster dendrogram. Three distinct groups of samples could be observed based on the H3K4me3 occupancy at the *H2AFX* gene.

Figure 5: The cluster dendrogram (left) showing H3K4me3 occupancy at *H2AFX* in INMA-Granada samples. Three groups could be observed with 41 samples in low-H2AFX group, 64 samples in medium-group and 14 samples in high H2AFX group (bar plot, right) Kruskal-Wallis's test, chi-squared = 94.632, df = 2, $p < 2.2 \cdot e^{-16}$ Pairwise Mann-Whitney).

For the analyses of the histone occupancy at the promoters of all the other genes tested in this study (Figure 5), the three groups that were observed based on H3K4me3 occupancy for *H2AFX* were maintained.

Figure 6: The graph represents the average values of copy numbers from Group 1 (blue) and Group 2 (green) and Group 3 (Red) for each gene normalised against *GAPDH*

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 18

Figure 7: Genomic view of H3K4me3 peaks for placenta (blue) and blood (red) and for BDNF (left) and KISS1 (right)

These preliminary results show that notably, for BDNF and KISS genes, primers could not be designed due to absence of H3K4me3 peaks in blood cells, suggesting the absence or very low expression of these factors in nucleated cells of the blood. This is in contrast to results obtained with placenta samples where these factors are present. The genomic view of H3K4me3 peaks for placenta (blue) and blood (red) and for BDNF (left) and KISS1 (right) is given in Figure 7 (below). It could be observed the very low peaks or absence of peaks for H3K4me3 in blood samples (red), while the presence of peaks in placenta (blue) for both genes. Therefore, both these genes can be analysed only by DNA methylation.

These results suggest that based on the levels of γ H2AX, which is a well-known marker of DNA damage (Mah et al., 2010), some samples have a high level of DNA damage, and these samples generally have high levels of H3K4me3 occupancy which could be due to higher transcriptional activity. It has been shown that women who smoked during pregnancy have hyperactive epigenetic state in several genes in their children persists into adolescence (Bauer et al., 2016). Nevertheless, these preliminary data should be confirmed, using for example, the comet assay. Additionally, pairwise comparisons have to be carried out to determine gene alterations between established groups.

5.2.3 References

- Mah LJ, El-Osta A, Karagiannis TC. 2010. γ H2AX: a sensitive molecular marker of DNA damage and repair. *Leukemia* 24(4):679-686.
- Bauer T, Trump S, Ishaque N, Thurmann L, Gu L, Bauer M, et al. 2016. Environment-induced epigenetic reprogramming in genomic regulatory elements in smoking mothers and their children. *Mol Syst Biol* 12(3):861.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 19

5.3 PART III

5.3.1 Characterisation of the Effect Biomarker: Telomere Length

INSERM completed previous data analysing the telomere length (TL) in the DNA of the same 124 boys from INMA-Granada cohort.

5.3.2 Methodology and Procedure

INSERM applied the qPCR method by using primers against hTERT. Ribosomal gene, 36B4, was used as the housekeeping gene. The primer sequences that were used are provided below. Briefly, forward and reverse primers for each gene (0.1 μ l each) and SYBR Green Supermix (BioRad) were mixed with each sample (0.05 ng/ μ l) and were loaded onto qPCR plates and was run on BioRad CFX 384 Real-time PCR system under normal qPCR thermal cycling conditions. The data was analysed by using the BioRad CFX Manager software.

Table 3: Forward and reverse primers employed

Gene	Forward Primer	Reverse primer
<i>hTERT</i>	GGTTTTGAGGGTGAGGGTGAGGGTGAGGGTGAGGGT	TCCCGACTATCCCTATCCCTATCCCTATCCCTATCCCTA
<i>36B4</i>	ACTGGTCTAGGACCCTAGAAG	TCAATGGTGCCTCTGGAGATT

5.3.3 Results

Unsupervised clustering of the samples show the existence of two groups with average normal [T/S (relative telomere to single copy gene) = 0.87] and long [T/S=1.49] telomere length in the DNA of boys from INMA-Granada, whereas grouping of samples based on H2AFX did not show any statistical difference in telomere length. The data needs to be reanalysed based on exposure data from UGR. The change in telomere length could serve as risk factor as changes in telomere were found in diseases and cancers (Haycock et al., 2017).

Figure 8: The Scatter plot (left) showing the telomere length in INMA-Granada samples. Unsupervised clustering (right) shows the existence of two groups with significant difference in telomere lengths.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 20

Figure 9: Grouping of samples based on histone occupancy at H2AFX gene do not show any significant difference in telomere length between groups.

5.3.4 References

Haycock PC, Burgess S, Nounu A, Zheng J, Okoli GN, Bowden J, et al. 2017. Association between telomere length and risk of cancer and non-neoplastic diseases: A Mendelian Randomisation Study. *JAMA Oncol* 3(5):636-651.

5.4 Conclusions from the epigenetic measurements in the blood of INMA-GRANADA Boys

1. DNA methylation at BDNF Exon IV shows alterations in CpGs in some of the tested samples. The data should be re-analysed by, for example, grouping the samples based on low and high-exposure to prioritised chemical compounds.
2. Analyses of histone H3K4me3 at nuclear receptors, DNA repair and detoxification genes show an increase in H3K4me3 peaks based on the group that was created on the basis of H2AFX levels. Pair-wise comparisons have to be carried out to determine gene alterations between established groups.
3. Analyses of telomere length in the DNA of boys from INMA-Granada shows presence of two groups with average normal [T/S (relative telomere to single copy gene) = 0.87] and longer (T/S=1.49) telomere length. These data should also be re-assessed based on exposure data.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 21

6 Antagonistic AR activity in placenta samples (UGR-DTU)

The human population is exposed to complex mixtures of myriads of chemical compounds. Chemicals can act together leading to a wide range of effects due to their combined activities. The human exposome is ever-changing as a result of changes in the chemical universe, such as introduction of new chemicals to the market and/or phase-out/banning of other chemicals. As a consequence, gaining information on whether the chemical mixture or components are problematic from a human health perspective is challenging.

Nowadays, male reproductive health and fertility is in the spotlight. The incidence of subfertile couples is increasing, as well as the incidence of boys with genitalia malformations, such as non-descendant testicles (cryptorchidism) (Main et al., 2010) and penile malformation (hypospadias) (Nassar et al., 2017). Additionally, the cases of testicular germ cell cancer (Chia et al., 2010) are increasing, while the sperm quality is decreasing in many countries (Levine et al., 2017). All these disorders are part of the so-called testicular dysgenesis syndrome (TDS), which is thought in part to be caused by chemical interferences with hormones systems, e.g. the androgen hormone system. Chemicals that can antagonise or inhibit the androgen receptor (AR), commonly known as ‘antiandrogenic chemicals’, could be able to disrupt the androgen signalling during critical windows of susceptibility alongside the foetal life (Shakkkebaek N.E., 2003).

With the aim of evaluating the combined effect of complex mixtures of chemicals present in human placenta samples, 5 different cell-based bioassays were performed. Thus, WP14 has already evaluated the biological activity exerted by mixtures of lipophilic halogenated compounds contained in the α -fraction extracted from 24 placentas from the INMA-Granada cohort (see “Proof of concept study”, D14.4 and AD14.4). The biological activity obtained using the AR-reporter gene assay (performed by DTU, see AD14.4), which evaluates the ability of the placenta α -fractions to inhibit the activity of the androgen receptor (AR), showed interesting results that deserved further investigation. Moreover, the screening developed in AD14.4 provided little information as to which chemicals were causing the biological effect measured with the selected bioassays. Thus, in order to gain further information on specific causative agents, an effect-directed analysis (EDA) approach has been initiated between DTU and UGR. Initially, this involves the subfractionation and testing of the previous α -fractions to gain information on whether the new specific subfractions are more or less active. In the end, the goal is to subject active subfractions to non-target analysis and thereby identify causative agents.

6.1.1 Strategy, materials and methods

6.1.1.1 Strategy

The EDA approach was based on the 6 following steps (collaborative work WP14-WP16). Very briefly:

1. DTU and UGR selected 8 placentas from the initial 24 placentas analysed in the “proof of concept” (see AD14.4), based on the antagonist androgenic activity obtained with the whole HPLC α -fractions. Eight placentas were selected, 4 with high and 4 with low antagonist androgenic activity.
2. Placenta homogenates were again extracted and fractionated following the previous semi-preparative HPLC procedure (see the extraction protocol at D14.4). In this approach 5 subfractions were collected compared with the traditional whole α -fraction extraction procedure (corresponding to the first HPLC 11 minutes) (see, D14.4). For each of the five

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 22

new subfractions, 2 minute HPLC elution was collected, except for the subfraction number 5, which included to the last 3 minutes (9-11 min) (Figure 10).

3. All 5 subfractions were tested in the AR EcoScreen in vitro assay in order to evaluate the antagonist AR-activity.
4. The subfraction number 5 that showed the highest antagonist AR-activity was again sub-fractionated in three 1 min fractions and re-analysed all three in the same in vitro assay for antagonistic AR-activity (Figure 11).
5. The sub-subfraction that showed the strongest antagonist AR-activity will be analysed in a non-target analysis (conducted by WP16), in order to identify chemical compound(s) in those active subsubfractions.
6. *Ad hoc* synthetic mixture made with the identified chemical compounds from the placentas subfractions will be tested in the AR reporter gene assay to establish whether they can explain the observed effects in the human α -fractions.

6.1.1.2 Materials and Methods

AR reporter gene assay

The AR EcoScreen assay is a well-known *in vitro* bioassay to assess the activation (induction or inhibition) of the AR, by either single chemicals or mixture of chemicals. In order to test the anti-androgenic potential of the subfractions, the bioassay is performed with a known amount of an inductor of the AR, metribolone (R1881). Chinese Hamster Ovary cell (CHO K1) were subcultured in Gibco® Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium F-12 Nutrient Mixture with L-glutamine and HEPES and without phenol red (DMEM/F-12) (Invitrogen™, Life Technologies™, Carlsbad, California, USA) supplemented with 5% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (Invitrogen™, Life Technologies™, Carlsbad, California, USA), 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin (Invitrogen™, Life Technologies™, Carlsbad, California, USA), 200µg/ml Zeocin™ Selection Reagent (Invitrogen™, Life Technologies™, Carlsbad, California, USA), and 100µg/ml Hygromycin B (Invitrogen™, Life Technologies™, Carlsbad, California, USA). After reaching 90% confluence, cells were passed with 0.05 % Trypsin-EDTA solution (Sigma-Aldrich®, St. Louis, Missouri, USA) and seeded in white, clear-bottom 96-wells plates at a density of 0.9×10^5 cell/mL at experimental medium, DMEM/F12 with 5% of FBS and 1% penicillin. CHO K1 cells were purchased from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, LGC standards, Borås, Sweden). Additionally, positive and negative controls using R1881 (PerkinElmer) and hydroxyflutamide (OHF) (Toronto Research Chemicals, Toronto, Canada), respectively, were conducted to assure the quality of the assay. R1881, was added to all wells at 0.1 nM in order to test the antagonist activity of the α -subfractions and α -sub-subfractions. Experimental medium was used as vehicle. All α -subfractions were tested in three concentrations (5, 10 and 20 mg of placenta per well), while α -sub-subfractions were tested in four concentrations (5, 10, 20 and 40 mg of placenta per well). All samples were tested in three independent experiments. The data showed makes reference to one experiment.

Figure 10: Procedure to extract and obtain placentas α -subfractions

Firefly luciferase activity was measured using Dual-Glo® Luciferase Assay System from Promega (Madison, Wisconsin, USA). To each well 100 µL Dual-Glo® Firefly were added and plates were shaken at room temperature for 15 minutes on an orbital shaker protected from light. Afterwards, luminescence was measured using the LUMIstar® Galaxy luminometer (BMG LABTECH, Offenburg, Germany).

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 24

Figure 11: Procedure to further fractionate the active subfractions. Each subfraction was fractionated into 3 sub-subfractiond (corresponding to 1 min elution time).

Cell viability

Cell viability was evaluated using Dual-Glo® Stop & Glo® Reagent from the Dual-Glo® Luciferase Assay System from Promega (Madison, Wisconsin, USA). Plates were supplemented with 50µl/well of Dual-Glo® Stop & Glo® and plates were placed at room temperature on an orbital shaker for approximately 15 min following measurement of Renilla luminescence using the LUMIstar® Galaxy luminometer (BMG LABTECH, Offenburg, Germany). A decrease of more than 20% of the renilla activity was considered as cytotoxic.

6.1.2 Results

A total number of 40 α-subfractions (5 for each of the 8 selected α-subfractions) and 24 α-subsubfractions (3 for each of the 8 α-fractions) were tested in the AR EcoScreen assay in antagonism mode.

Effects on cell viability were observed in a few cases. Cell viability was compromised in subfractions of placenta no. 10, 11, and 25 at the highest concentrations of subfraction 4. In placenta no. 21, cell viability was compromised at the highest concentrations of subfraction 5. Overall, the AR activity was antagonised in a concentration-dependent manner by subfraction 5, whereas this trend was not observed for the remaining subfractions (Figure 12).

Figure 12: AR antagonistic activity of α -subfractions

Based on the above results, subfraction 5 was selected for further fractionation. For α -subsubfractions (Figure 13), cell viability was compromised in placentas no. 10, 14, 15, 21 and 25 at the highest concentrations of sub-subfraction 2, while in placenta no. 11, cell viability was compromised at the highest concentration of sub-subfraction 3. The blocking of the AR activity was exerted in a concentration-dependent manner in subsubfraction 2 of placentas no. 10, 13, 14, 15, 21 and 25, corresponding to the minute 10 of the elution, whereas in placentas no. 6 and 11, the concentration-dependent inhibition of the AR was produced by subsubfraction 3, which corresponds to the minute 11 of the elution.

Figure 13: AR antagonistic activity of α -subsubfractions

Summary

Almost all tested subfractions #5 showed a concentration-dependent antagonistic effect of the AR.

Additionally, further fractionation of this subfraction #5, showed that the activity was located in subsubfraction 3 from placentas no. 6 and 11, in which a concentration-dependent antagonism of the AR was seen. However, in placentas no. 10, 13, 14, 15, 21 and no. 25, further fractionation revealed that the AR antagonistic activity was observed in subsubfraction 5.2, in which a concentration-dependent antagonism of the AR was seen.

Partners from WP16 will receive these relevant subsubfractions for non-target analysis. These samples will be selected to enhance the identification of causative agents after discussions with all partners. The subsubfractions will be shipped in January 2020 to the relevant French WP16 partners.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 27

6.1.3 References

- Chia, V.M., Li, Y., Quraishi, S.M., Graubard, B.I., Figueroa, J.D., Weber, J.-P., Chanock, S.J., Rubertone, M. V, Erickson, R.L., McGlynn, K.A., 2010. Effect modification of endocrine disruptors and testicular germ cell tumour risk by hormone-metabolizing genes. *Int. J. Androl.* 33, 588–96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2605.2009.00975.x>
- Levine, H., Jørgensen, N., Martino-Andrade, A., Mendiola, J., Weksler-Derri, D., Mindlis, I., Pinotti, R., Swan, S.H., 2017. Temporal trends in sperm count: A systematic review and meta-regression analysis. *Hum. Reprod. Update* 23, 646–659. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humupd/dmx022>
- Main, K.M., Skakkebaek, N.E., Virtanen, H.E., Toppari, J., 2010. Genital anomalies in boys and the environment. *Best Pract. Res. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beem.2009.10.003>
- Schneuer, F.J., Bentley, J.P., Holland, A.J.A., Lain, S.J., Jamieson, S.E., Badawi, N., Nassar, N., 2017. Early childhood development of boys with genital anomalies. *Birth defects Res.* 109, 535–542. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdra.23603>
- Skakkebaek, N.E., 2003. Testicular dysgenesis syndrome. In: *Hormone Research*. p. 49. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000074499>

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 28

7 Xenoestrogenic transactivity of placenta extracts containing PFAS mixtures (AU)

7.1.1 Description of the Bioassay/Effect Biomarker

Perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) are synthetic chemical surfactants used as detergents or impregnating agents in numerous industrial applications, such as paper and packaging (food and non-food applications) as well as textile finishing (Kotthoff et al 2015). Humans are mainly exposed to these persistent chemicals through food items and drinking water (Haug et al., 2010). Exposure studies to individual PFAS suggest that PFAS may interfere with the estrogen system both *in vitro* (Kjeldsen et al., 2013; Henry et al., 2013) and in humans (Itoh et al., 2016; Lopez-Espinosa et al., 2016). Humans are, however, exposed to complex PFAS mixtures and studies of the combined effect of these mixtures on human health have been limited due to the complexity of studying combinations of chemicals. AU WP14 partner has recently showed that the combined effects of PFAA mixtures present in serum of 702 Danish pregnant women affected human fetal growth by disrupting the ER (estrogen receptor) pathway. They we found associations between higher xenoestrogenic activities induced by serum PFAA extracts with lower birth weight and shorter birth length in the offspring (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al., 2019).

For this reason and following the same protocol, AU aimed to extract the PFAS mixture present in 24 placenta homogenates, selected and studied in the “proof of concept” (see AD14.4), to determine the derived xenoestrogenic activity of the PFAS extracts.

7.1.2 Methodology and Procedure

AU extracted the PFAS mixtures from the 24 placenta samples using solid phase extraction (SPE), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), and weak anion exchange (WAX). The PFAA-induced xenoestrogenic receptor transactivation was determined using the stable transfected MVLN cell line.

PFAS extraction from placenta homogenates: In this study, it was followed the same protocol used to extract PFAS mixtures from serum samples, slightly modified, using a solid-phase extraction technique for sample extraction and purification, and liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry. The eluate was collected in several fractions with the PFAAs in fraction F3. Fraction F3 was further extracted by weak anion exchange on an OASIS WAX cartridge. The PFAAs were eluted using 0.1% ammonium hydroxide in methanol in a fraction referred to as F3-W2 (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al., 2015). In each extraction batch, a procedural blank consisting of hexane were included and analysed in parallel.

In this pilot assay, we extracted the F3-W2 fraction from different amount of placenta homogenates (2g, 6g, 10g and 16g) and tested the xeno-estrogen transactivity of the different extracts, being the amount of 16 g of placenta homogenate the best to obtain useful test concentrations.

The 16 g of placenta homogenates were dissolved in hexane and passed through a glass column with Aluminium oxide 90 standardised (CAS #: 1344-28-1, Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany) that had been dried at 600°C for minimum 4 hr and hydrated with 5% water. The eluate was evaporated using a rotary evaporator, before the SPE-HPLC-WAX extraction (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al., 2015). Briefly, the extracts were subjected to SPE (OASIS HLB, Waters) and liquid–liquid extraction (Hexane:EtOAc 9:1). The aqueous phase, containing PFAS, was further extracted with liquid–liquid extraction (tetrahydrofuran:hexane 3:2), HPLC fractionation and finally a WAX (OASIS WAX, Waters), as described in Bjerregaard-Olesen et al. 2015 (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al., 2015).

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 29

The placenta extracts containing PFAS mixtures (fraction F3-W2) were evaporated by vacuum centrifugation, and the dry fractions were stored at -80°C until determination of the PFAS related xeno-estrogenic activity.

Xenoestrogenic transactivity measurement: In this study, AU employs the established estrogenic transactivation assay using the human cancer cell line MVLN that derives from the human breast carcinoma MCF-7 cell line, stably transfected with a reporter gene construct, pVit-tk-Luc (Bonefeld-Jorgensen et al., 2005). The gene construct contains a luciferase gene under control of the estrogen response element (ERE), as previously described (Bonefeld-Jorgensen et al. 2005).

The estrogenic and anti-estrogenic transactivation of the PFAS placenta extracts (F3-W2) was determined using the stably transfected MVLN cell line (Bonefeld-Jorgensen et al., 2006). Briefly, 8.5×10^4 cells were seeded in each well in a 96-well plate and incubated overnight (37°C and 5% CO₂). The next day (24 h later), the dry placenta extracts (F3-W2) were reconstituted in 20 µL EtOH:H₂O:DMSO (50:40:10, v/v/v) and 200 µL of Dulbecco's modified Eagle's media without phenol red (DMEM, Lonza) containing 0.5% charcoal-dextran stripped fetal bovine serum. These solutions were then divided into two portions of 100 µL each, which were diluted with 400 µL DMEM media (i.e. non-competitive design, XER) or 400 µL DMEM media containing 30 pM E₂ (i.e. competitive design with a final E₂ concentration of 24 pM, XERcomp) (Bonefeld-Jorgensen et al., 2006). The reconstituted PFAS fractions (F3-W2), with and without, 17β-estradiol (E₂) co-exposure were added to the 96-well plate in triplicate, using 100 µL/well. After 24 hours exposure, the cells were harvested. The induced luciferase activity was determined using a luminometer (BMG LUMISTAR) with automatic injection of luciferase substrate and data expressed as relative light units (RLU). The luciferase data were corrected for cell density referred as the protein content in each well determined by addition of 50 µl/well of fluorescamine diluted in acetonitrile (500 mg/l), followed by fluorometric measurements in a Wallac VICTOR2 (Perkin Elmer) at 355/460 nm wavelength. The estrogenic transactivation was expressed as relative light units per count of protein (RLU/prot).

The xeno-estrogenic receptor transactivation for the PFAS extracts alone in the non-competitive assay (XER) and upon co-exposure with E₂ in the competitive assay (XERcomp) was expressed as percentage of the procedural blank ± E₂ (set to 100%).

7.1.3 Results

AU first visually assessed the health of the cell in a microscope, using the extracted the F3-W2 fraction from different amount of placenta homogenates (2g, 6g, 10g and 16g), and did not observe any signs of cytotoxicity (data not shown).

Half of the placenta PFAS extracts, assessed in the XER [13 of the 25 (52%)] increased significantly the estrogen receptor (ER) transactivity. Moreover, 68% of the placenta extracts further enhanced the activity of the natural ligand E₂. No extracts decreased the ER transactivity significantly (Figure 14). The median fold induction was 110 % [Interquartile range (IQR): 13.8] of the procedural blank, with a minimum of 93% and a maximum of 128%.

Figure 14: Estrogen receptor transactivity of placenta extracts tested alone. *: Transactivity of the sample significantly different from the procedural blank

In the presence of the natural estrogen ligand, E₂, 17 of the 25 (68%) placenta PFAS extracts significantly enhanced the E₂-induced transactivity and no samples antagonised the transactivity significantly (Figure 15). The median fold induction was 124 % (IQR: 18.5) of the procedural blank+E₂ with a minimum of 88% and a maximum of 144%.

Figure 15: Estrogen receptor transactivity of extracts tested in the present of estrogen (E₂, 24 pM). *: Transactivity of the sample significantly different from the procedural blank.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 31

7.1.4 Strengths and limitations

With the applied method, WP14 has been able to determine the combined xenoestrogen transactivity of PFAS mixtures present in placenta homogenates. In the extraction procedure, we included a procedural blank (hexane), treated in parallel with all the samples.

With the ER transactivity assay, we are able to detect PFAS mixture induced estrogen activities mediated through the ER receptor. We included several controls in the assay to ensure the reliability of the results. In each plate, we included a medium control, a solvent control and a positive control (24 pM E₂; E₂-EC₅₀). We also included a titration plate with a dilution serial of an ER agonist (E₂). The intra-assay 'Coefficient of Variation' for the controls were below 10 %, indicating high precision of the measurement.

AU has previously used a similar extraction method to extract PFAS mixtures from human serum samples with recoveries between 49.6% and 78.6% (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al., 2015). AU assumes comparable recoveries for the PFAS extracted from the placenta homogenates; however, the additional steps of dissolving the homogenates and elution through Aluminium oxide column may affect the final recoveries. This could be explored further in future validation studies.

7.1.5 Conclusions

The 52% of the F3-W2 placenta extracts (containing PFAS mixtures) tested showed a significantly induced of xeno-estrogenic transactivity and 68% of the placenta extracts further enhanced the activity of the natural ligand E₂. In future studies, the presence of individual PFAS in the placenta homogenates extract could be determined.

7.1.6 References

- Bjerregaard-Olesen C, Bach CC, Long M, Wielsoe M, Bech BH, Henriksen TB, et al. Associations of fetal growth outcomes with measures of the combined xenoestrogenic activity of maternal serum perfluorinated alkyl acids in Danish pregnant women. *Environ Health Perspect* 2019;127(1):17006.
- Bjerregaard-Olesen C, Bossi R, Bech BH, Bonfeld-Jorgensen EC. Extraction of perfluorinated alkyl acids from human serum for determination of the combined xenoestrogenic transactivity: a method development. *Chemosphere* 2015;129:232-8.
- Bonfeld-Jorgensen EC, Grunfeld HT, Gjermansen IM. Effect of pesticides on estrogen receptor transactivation in vitro: a comparison of stable transfected MVLN and transient transfected MCF-7 cells. *Mol Cell Endocrinol* 2005;244(1-2):20-30.
- Bonfeld-Jorgensen EC, Hjelmberg PS, Reinert TS, Andersen BS, Lesovoy V, Lindh CH, et al. Xenoestrogenic activity in blood of European and Inuit populations. *Environ Health* 2006;5:12.
- Haug LS, Salihovic S, Jogsten IE, Thomsen C, van Bavel B, Lindstrom G, et al. Levels in food and beverages and daily intake of perfluorinated compounds in Norway. *Chemosphere* 2010;80(10):1137-43.
- Henry ND, Fair PA. Comparison of in vitro cytotoxicity, estrogenicity and anti-estrogenicity of triclosan, perfluorooctane sulfonate and perfluorooctanoic acid. *J Appl Toxicol* 2013;33(4):265-72.
- Itoh S, Araki A, Mitsui T, Miyashita C, Goudarzi H, Sasaki S, et al. Association of perfluoroalkyl substances exposure in utero with reproductive hormone levels in cord blood in the Hokkaido Study on Environment and Children's Health. *Environ Int* 2016;94:51-9.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 32

Kjeldsen LS, Bonfeld-Jorgensen EC. Perfluorinated compounds affect the function of sex hormone receptors. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 2013;20(11):8031-44.

Kotthoff M, Müller J, Jürling H, Schlummer M, Fiedler D. Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in consumer products. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2015;22(19):14546-59.

Lopez-Espinosa MJ, Mondal D, Armstrong BG, Eskenazi B, Fletcher T. Perfluoroalkyl Substances, Sex hormones, and insulin-like growth factor-1 at 6-9 years of age: A Cross-Sectional analysis within the C8 Health project. *Environ Health Perspect* 2016;124(8):1269-75.

AD14.6 - Report on the state of development of Task 14.3: Identification of needs for the implementation of both classical and new biomarkers of effect and decision criteria for their validation	Security: Public
WP14 – Effect Biomarkers	Version: 1.1
Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea, Mariana F. Fernández	Page: 33

8 Conclusions and Future Steps

1. This preliminary pilot study with INMA-Granada birth cohort human samples shows the technical feasibility to implement novel biomarkers of brain function such as BDNF, at different levels of biological organisation, in the HBM4EU aligned studies, although at this stage, no conclusions for the possible applicability of the BDNF marker for HBM4EU settings can be taken. Future steps could include the implementation of these novel biomarkers of brain function in the HBM4EU aligned studies during 2020 based on these results obtained with the INMA-Granada pilot study. Additionally, UGR and INSERM will analyse and integrate all exposure, effect and outcome data available for neurodevelopment in the INMA-Granada study.
2. Apart from BDNF measurements in serum and blood, the measurement of BDNF concentrations in urine samples is being explored by UGR. Currently, the specific ELISA kit with the best performance in urine has been identified. During the next month, UGR will conduct quality control measures to ensure that reproducibility and inter-assay variability criteria are fulfilled.
3. The use of cell-based bioassays may help to better understand how chemical mixtures contained in human samples may exert combined biological activities. The advantage of using bioassays is: i) that an integrated effect or a biological fingerprint is measured, taking into account plausible mixture effects and ii) that bioassays can help in identifying both known and new chemicals of concern in human tissues. In this regards, UGR and DTU identified for the first time some placenta subfractions which showed the highest antiandrogenic activity. Future steps will include the non-targeted chemical profiling of the biologically active subfractions (interaction with WP16), in order to identify and understand exposure-activity relationships in a real-world scenario.
4. The development of the PFAS mixture isolation (AU) opens the possibility of assessing specific chemical families isolated from human samples, with direct implications for risk assessment and policy making. Before this isolation, biomarkers of combined activity were tested with alpha-fractions, which include very complex chemical mixtures while trying to exclude endogenous hormones. In collaboration with WP16, the validation of this PFAS mixture isolation by analysing the PFAS recoveries would have important implications, since the information derived from this PFAS mixture isolation could and should be integrated into risk assessment procedures. Future steps include further testing other combined biological activities of the isolated mixture of PFAS from placenta samples, and explore the isolation of PFAS and other chemical families in other more convenient biological samples for HBM studies such as blood. Additionally, before further steps are taken, existing results must be substantiated and verified.